

Specific surface area- Titration

**Deliverable 3.3, SOPs for all Physicochemical Methods,
Annex I, page 131.**

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SPECIFIC SURFACE AREA IN COLLOIDAL SILICA				

1 SUMMARY

The sample of colloidal silica is titrated with NaOH from pH 4 to pH 9, in a medium of 20 % NaCl(aq). A fraction of the OH⁻ ions will bind to the surface of the silica particles, and the amount of “free” OH⁻ contributing to the pH increase from 4 to 9 will therefore depend on the total surface area of the silica particles.

2 GENERAL INFORMATION

A copy of this instruction can be found in folder 10, labeled BMA.rkt BMA.

3 HAZARDS AND SAFETY

Most products of colloidal silica are strongly alkaline. In the event of eye contact, colloidal silica can be difficult to rinse off due to the high concentration of silica particles. Use eye protection (goggles), gloves and general laboratory clothing.

4 QUALITY ASSURANCE OF ANALYTICAL METHOD

A control sample (30/220) is analyzed weekly, and at every occasion of analysis. New control sample can be acquired from the factory. The specific surface area of the two replicates from the same sample should not differ more than 20 m²/g. The pH electrode is calibrated at every occasion of analysis, and is controlled with a pH 9 QP-buffer. The uncertainty of the method is 3 % for products with high specific surface area (700-900 m²/g) and 8 % for products with specific surface area <100 m²/g.

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5 APPARATUS

- 5.1 Titration system (Titrande), equipped with the Tiamo software from Metrohms
- 5.2 pH electrode, ROSS Sure-Flow (Orion)
- 5.3 Plastic beaker, 250 ml
- 5.4 Magnetic stirring bar, 30 mm

6 CHEMICALS

- 6.1 Sodium Chloride, NaCl, p a
- 6.2 HCl, 0,1 mol/l
- 6.3 HCl, 1 mol/l
- 6.4 NaOH, 0,1 mol/l
- 6.5 pH buffers: pH 4, 9 and 10
- 6.6 Cat-ion exchange resins
 - 6.6.1 ROHM and Haas 1500 H (rinsed according to section 10.4.1)
 - 6.6.2 Dow Amberlite HPR 650 H (rinsed according to section 10.4.2)

7 PROCEEDURE

Samples containing $\text{Al}^{3+} > 0.1 \%$ or $\text{NH}_3 > 0.001 \%$ must ion exchanged prior to analysis (see section 7.3).

- 7.1 Assessing the SiO_2 concentration of the sample

- 7.1.1 Samples with available density table data:

The density of the sample is measured (see section 7.3) and the SiO_2 concentration is derived from the density table for the particular product.

- 7.1.2 Samples without density table data:

For samples that have been ion-exchanged, and other products for which no density table is available, the SiO_2 concentration must be determined by XRF before analysis.

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7.2 Preparation of the pH electrode
Change the electrode solution, and calibrate the pH electrode using buffers with pH 4 and 10. Check the accuracy of the electrode using buffer with pH 9.

7.3 Sample preparation and titration of Na⁺-stabilized products
Time requirement: 30 min.
All utensils must be made of plastic.

Mix the sample.

In a plastic beaker, weigh an amount of sample corresponding to an amount of 1,5 g SiO₂ for products with specific surface area < 700 m²/g, or 1 g SiO₂ for products with specific surface area > 700 m²/g (see section 8.1).

Adjust the volume to 80 ml with de-ionized water. Make two replicates for each sample.

Adjust the pH to 3,0 - 3,5 using HCl (0,1 mol/l or 1 mol/l).

Add 30,0 g of NaCl adjust the volume to 150 ml with de-ionized water. Stir the mixture to dissolve the NaCl.

Titrate the solution with the Titrando system, with the stirring speed set to 4-6. Use the following program depending on the expected surface area:

Tiamo program	Surface (m ² /g)
EXLÅG	< 70
LÅG	70 - 150
MELLAN	150 - 400
HÖG	> 400

Ensure that the start and stop pH are 4,00 - 4,10 and 9,00 - 9,02 respectively.

7.4 Ion exchange, sample preparation and titration of products stabilized with Al³⁺ or NH³⁺.
The aluminium ions bound to the surface are exchanged by lowering the pH to < 3. Al³⁺ and Na⁺ are removed from the solution using an ion exchange resin before analysis.

Time requirement 1 h 15 min.

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Mix the sample.

Add 50 ml of ion exchange resin to a 250 ml plastic beaker, using a 50 ml plastic scoop.

Add 100 ml of sample using a plastic graduated cylinder.

Measure the pH of the mixture, and adjust to pH < 2,5 using 0,1 M HCl, if necessary.

Stir the mixture for 30 min to allow ion exchange. For Pursol 14-400 products (ammonium stabilized) it is enough with 10 min to reach ion exchange.

Ensure that the pH has not changed during the ion exchange.

Provide 12 ml of sample in a nunc beaker to the XRF lab for analysis of the SiO₂ concentration.

For aluminium stabilized products, ensure that the concentration of Al₂O₃ reported by XRF is < 0.1 %. If the Al₂O₃ concentration is > 0.1 %, the sample must be ion exchanged again.

If the sample is coagulated during ion exchange (typical for samples with high specific surface area), make a new batch of ion exchange resin, adjust the volume to 25-50 ml with deionized water and carefully add the colloidal silica in small aliquots while stirring the mixture.

In a plastic beaker, weigh an amount of sample corresponding to an amount of 1,5 g SiO₂ for products with specific surface area < 700 m²/g, or 1 g SiO₂ for products with specific surface area > 700 m²/g (see section 8.1).

Adjust the volume to 80 ml with de-ionized water. Make two replicates for each sample.

Add 30,0 g of NaCl adjust the volume to 150 ml with de-ionized water. Stir the mixture to dissolve the NaCl.

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Titrate the solution with the Titrando system, with the stirring speed set to 4-6. Use the following program depending on the expected surface area:

Tiamo program	Surface (m ² /g)
EXLÅG	< 70
LÅG	70 - 150
MELLAN	150 - 400
HÖG	> 400

Ensure that the start and stop pH are 4,00 - 4,10 and 9,00 - 9,02 respectively.

8 CALCULATING AND REPORTING

8.1 Calculation of the amount of sample before weighing

$$\text{Required sample weight} = \frac{1,50 \times 100}{\% \text{SiO}_2} = \frac{150}{\% \text{SiO}_2}$$

1,50 : desired amount of SiO₂ (g)
 100 : conversion factor % to g
 % SiO₂ : silica concentration of the sample

8.2 Calculation of the specific surface area (built into the Tiamo software):

$$\text{Specific surface area} = \frac{1,50 \times 100 \times V_{\text{NaOH}} \times 32}{W \times \text{wt}\%} - 25 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$$

1,50 : desired amount of SiO₂ (g)
 100 : conversion factor % to g
 V_{NaOH} : volume of 0,1 mol/l NaOH (ml) required to rise the pH from 4 to 9
 32 : proportionality constant between V_{NaOH} and specific surface area (see reference 11.1)
 W : sample weight (g)
 25 : intercept for the linear relationship between titer volume and specific surface area (see ref 11.1)
 wt% : SiO₂ concentration of the sample

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Even if the sample weight is adjusted for a desired amount of 1 g SiO₂, the factor 1,50 g should be used in order to compensate the titer volume so that it corresponds to 1,50 g SiO₂.

8.3 Reporting

Report the concentrations in units of Unit: m²/g.

For produces with specific surface area > 100 m²/g, the reported value is rounded off to the nearest ten. For products with specific surface area <100 m²/g, the reported value is rounded off to the nearest integer.

9 WASTE DISPOSAL

All solutions can be poured out in the sink.

10 ADDITIONAL INSTRUCTIONS

10.1 Rinsing of the pH-electrode

After each day of usage, the electrode is rinsed by water, immersed in 1 mol/l NaOH for 30 min under stirring, and thereafter rinsed again with water. The electrode is thereafter stored in de-ionized water.

10.2 Troubleshooting

If the calibration is unsuccessful or takes a long time:

1. Replace the buffer solution, firstly the pH 10 solution
2. If the electrode reacts slowly, immerse t in 0,1 mol/l HCl for 5
10 min
3. Replace the electrode

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10.3 Parameters for the different titer programs in Tiamo

Method	Yta EXLÅG	Yta LÅG	Yta MELLAN	Yta HÖG
For surface area (m ² /g):	<70	70-150	150-400	>400
SET1 pH 4				
Dynamics pH	3	3	3	3
Max rate (ml/min)	2	2	2	2
Min rate (µl/min)	10	20	20	20
Stop criterion	Drift	Drift	Drift	Drift
Drift criterion (µl/min)	100	100	100	100
SET2 pH 9				
Dynamics pH	3	2	2	1
Max rate (ml/min)	5	10	10	50
Min rate (ul/min)	10	20	100	100
Stop criterion	Drift	Drift	Drift	Drift
Drift criterion (µl/min)	100	100	100	100

10.4 Rinsing of cat-ion exchange resin

The cat-ion resins currently used (ROHM and Haas 1500 H) will be replaced with a single type of strong cat-ion resing (Dow Amberlite HPR 650 H).

Re-generated cat-ion exchange resing can be aquired from the colloidal silica factory. It has been treated with acid and must be rinsed with water before use.

10.4.1 Rinsing of ROHM and Haas 1500 H

The new re-generated ion-exchange resin is rinsed with de-ionized water until the pH has reached pH 3,5 – 4,5. Pour the resin into a plastic beaker and flush with de-ionized water for 1-2 h. Transfer a small amount of the resin with water to a separate beaker for measuring the pH. Store the resin in 1,5 l resealable plastic bottles. The resin must neither be dry nor too wet.

10.4.2 Rinsing off Dow Amberlite HPR 650 H

The new re-renerated ion exchange resin is added to a 5 l plastic beaker. The beaker is filled up with de-ionized water. The water is poured off and the beaker is filled up with new water. The procedure is repeated 2-3 times, or until the pH has reached 3,5-

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4,5. Transfer a small amount of the resin with water to a separate beaker for measuring the pH. Store the resin in 1,5 l resealable plastic bottles. The resin must neither be dry nor too wet.

11 REFERENCES

- 11.1 Sears, G.W. Determination of specific surface area of silica by titration with sodium hydroxide, Analytical Chemistry 28,1981 (1956).
- 11.2 Gunnarsson, M. Measurement uncertainty for the specific surface area of silica sols. Report, Eka Chemicals CA2010-005
- 11.3 Gunnarsson, M. Method parameters for the analysis of specific surface area of silica sols. Report, Eka Chemicals CA2011-028
- 11.4 Instruction FU139 – Handhavande av titrerprogrammet Tiamo och titrerutrustning kopplad till programmet.